

README – Research Documentation Package

Dataset for the conference paper:

Use of the vAdBeCeDa Mobile Application for Promoting Physical Activity in Older Adults: Analysis of User Experience and Behavioral Impact

Authors

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Study Description

The study evaluated the usability, understandability and perceived impact of the vAdBeCeDa mobile application for promoting physical activity among older adults in Slovenia. Data were collected through educational and practical workshops introducing participants to the application.

Methods

A mixed-methods evaluation approach was used, combining structured questionnaire responses and qualitative feedback from open-ended questions.

Number of workshops: 74

Number of participants: 1,087

Repository Contents

- README document
- Evaluation questionnaire
- Supporting documentation

Data Availability Statement

The repository contains the evaluation questionnaire and supporting documentation used in the study. The underlying individual-level data are not publicly available because they originate from an internal evaluation process and may contain information that could indirectly identify participants. Additional information may be requested from the corresponding author.

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